

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART VI. ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRECIPITATION AND GELATION OF RESINS

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Precipitation and gelation curves of de-waxed shellac in a solvent mixture of acetone containing 10% by weight of glycol were determined with a view to elucidating the mechanism of the formation of varnish films in which gel-formation plays an important role.

It is an established fact that a sol forms a thermo-reversible gel on cooling, only when the concentration of the lyophilic solute is above a minimum (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1926, p. 700; Mardles, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 118). If the concentration of the solute is below this minimum, precipitation of a portion of the dispersed phase occurs. The gelation temperature (*i.e.* sol-gel transformation point) *versus* concentration curves have been determined for many lyophilic substances, but it has so far not been possible to determine their precipitation curve (which is of course identically the same as the solubility curve) below minimum gelation concentration. This lack of data is ascribed to two reasons. Firstly, the minimum gelation concentration is very small for most substances and hence investigation into this region is very difficult. Secondly, even if it were possible to investigate such low concentrations, which will necessarily have inconveniently low precipitation temperatures, reliable data would hardly be obtained due to supercooling, interferences from the colloidal nature of the solute and other disturbing factors.

Natural resins and synthetic resins of low molecular weight do not offer any of the above difficulties. Their minimum gelation concentrations generally lie between 25 and 44% concentration of the resin and secondly, their precipitation temperature can be determined with great accuracy, since a number of them have been observed (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 253) to behave in solution more like partially miscible binary or ternary systems than like ordinary solid solutes. Hence, here is a chance of determining the precipitation and the gelation curve of the same substance in the same solvent, and the present communication describes results of investigations with this object in view. Although the results obtained are of a preliminary nature, they are considered sufficiently important to be worthy of record at this initial stage, since the results can throw much light on some vexed questions about gelation. The work is, however, being followed up to elucidate the mechanism of varnish film formation during which gel formation plays an important role.

As the resin, shellac has been chosen for study. The proper choice of solvents is an essential pre-requisite to success in such experiments. For

example, if alcohol is used for such determination with shellac, the gelation and precipitation temperatures are too low at small concentrations to be experimentally determined.

FIG. 1.

Intersection point of the curves represents 'C'.

The experiments have been conducted with de-waxed shellac as the resin, and acetone containing 10% by weight of glycol as the solvent mixture. This composition of the solvent mixture has been chosen after much preliminary experiments with various combinations, since this composition produces precipitation and gelation in a very conveniently workable temperature range. The precipitation and gelation points have been determined by very simple methods of gradually cooling the solutions contained in thin test tubes. Precipitation point is determined by noting the temperature at which opalescence starts. The temperature at which, in about 15 minutes, the liquid ceases to flow on inversion of the test tube is taken as the gelation point.

Before discussing about the curves, it should be mentioned, as explained in a previous paper (Palit, *loc. cit.*), that the precipitation temperature can be

All ordinary common solvents for shellac were found to be too good solvents to be employed in such experiments. Hence, the author has been forced to use a mixture of solvents, which would give precipitation and gelation in the easily measurable region of temperature scale. Of course, there is absolutely no reason, why such a suitable resin-pure solvent system should not exist, but failing to discover such a type of combination as meets our requirement, the author has resorted to the next best, *i.e.* a suitable mixture of solvents. The experimental results are shown graphically in Fig. 1.

determined very precisely to an accuracy of 0.1° , more precisely towards the rapidly falling portion of the curve BC (curve on the left). The gelation temperature can be reproduced to an accuracy of 0.2 , and the difference between gelation temperature and the melting point of the gel, unlike all other jellies, is very small, seldom exceeding 0.4° . A relieving feature of these experiments is that the gelation temperature is free from any appreciable lag, i.e., it is practically independent of the rate of cooling. The data for very low concentrations of shellac (portion AB) are much less accurate than indicated above due to the difficulty of noting the exact beginning of precipitation, and due to a comparative lack of the high degree of reversibility which exists for higher concentrations (portion BC).

The curves ACD are self-explanatory: the portion AC is the precipitation curve, whereas CD (curve on the right) is the gelation curve. The most characteristic and unexpected feature of the precipitation curve is that leaving out a small initial portion of the curve, the solutions become thermally stabler, the higher the concentration of the solute; in other words, a solution which contains 30% shellac requires more cooling for precipitation than a solution of 20% strength. The gelation curve, however, has the usual feature of having a higher gelation temperature for higher concentration of shellac. The dotted portions are actually realisable by suitable adjustments of experimental conditions, as is to be shortly explained. The first unstable point, (indicated by dotted circles) as occurring with at 32.5% shellac solution, indicates that if such a solution is slowly cooled below 10.4° , the whole thing becomes turbid due to precipitation of a new phase. But, if, on the other hand, it is very rapidly cooled, below 9° , a slightly hazy elastic gel forms, which slowly becomes turbid due to precipitation of the resin. The first distinctly visible insoluble mass separates in about 5 to 10 minutes. The next unstable point corresponding to a concentration of 35% shellac is of a slightly different significance. On cooling such a solution it becomes an elastic non-flowing gel at 11.2° . On further cooling, nothing happens until the temperature goes below 9.6° , when the gel becomes turbid due to copious precipitation. In fact, the gel was kept for 5 hours between 9.8° and 10° without the slightest opalescence occurring, whereas at 9.2° copious precipitation occurred in 15 minutes. The third and the other unstable points have similar significance, except that it takes more time for precipitation to start as the solution gets more and more concentrated. For a 50% solution, gelation occurs at 25.2° , whereas precipitation could not be induced on keeping at 0° for 24 hours, though the extrapolated precipitation temperature from the curve would be at about 2° .

The outstanding feature of the curves is that they divide the whole region into four parts and clearly sets forth the condition under which

a gel should be stable or unstable. But whatever may be the type of gel, the results clearly establish that the precipitation curve is quite distinct and separate from the gelation curve. It has been upheld in some quarters (Von Weimarn, Alexander's "Colloid Chemistry," Vol. I, p. 81; Lloyd, *ibid*, p. 777; Weimarn and Hagiwara, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1927, 23, 400) that gelation is a limiting case of precipitation and Bradford (*Biochem. J.*, 1918, 12, 351; 1920, 14, 29, 74) goes so far as to suppose that the precipitate is crystalline. If it is so, the precipitation curve and gelation curve should be a continuation of each other. The results obtained in these experiments not only discredit such a theory, but explicitly show that a resin gel does not differ from the solution, from which it is derived by cooling, in so far as its property to precipitate a new phase is concerned, since both are given by the same precipitation curve. We have shown in a previous publication (Palit, *loc. cit.*), that a resin-solvent system is a mutual true solution, which is undoubtedly non-colloidal at least when dilute and hence, a resin gel is to be regarded as a mutual true solution of the resin and the solvent which has attained such a high viscosity as to lose its property to flow. That during transition from a viscous sol to an elastic gel, no abrupt change in properties occur (Laing and McBain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1506; Brouse, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1929, 21, 242) is also known for soap and casein.

In the case of resin gels, we have thus been forced to depart from the usually accepted diphasic structure of gels. Of course, Procter, Katz and others, long ago, were inclined to view the protein gels as homogeneous systems (Procter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 313; Procter and Wilson, *ibid.*, 1916, 109, 307; Katz, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1917, 9, 1; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 279), and Fischer (Fischer and Hooker, "Lyophilic Colloids", 1933, p. 3; *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 51, 39) in a series of papers attempted to bring forward evidences for his theory of 'inverse solution' for gels. It should be noted that these resin solutions and also many other systems are true molecular solutions and they are capable of forming reversible optically clear gels. Before advancing a colloidal theory for such gels, it is yet to be proved that reversible micellar aggregation takes place. On the other hand, unless the present state of knowledge on solvation (for a discussion *vide* Heymann, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 846; 1938, 34, 689) is improved, it is useless to attempt to show how such immobilisation can be effected by solvation alone.

We have now to explain why shellac gels are so reversible in character, whilst most lyophilic gels show pronounced lag and hysteresis. Thus the setting and melting points of an agar gel may differ by as much as 60°, while

a difference of 5° or 10° is very common. This difference in character is manifest even in the viscosity behaviour of these gels. Whereas a shellac gel regains its original viscosity on melting within the short time by which temperature equilibrium is established (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 308), most lyophilic gels show considerable hysteresis. The explanation certainly lies in the nature of solvation of the unit in solution. It is probable that solvation itself is reversible for shellac due to its small molecule of rather not complicated shape being the ultimate unit in solution, while for the lyophilic colloids, the ultimate unit being either the micelle or the molecule of giant size, the adsorption of solvent is much less reversible. This can be more easily understood when it is recognised, as pointed out by Ostwald (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 46, 248) and by Haller (*ibid.*, 1929, 48, 47; 1931, 56, 257), that solvent molecules may remain held up even in absence of adsorption forces, in the various pockets and channels formed inside the micelle or inside the too big molecule due to its peculiar geometrical shape.

The data being very meagre, to explore further the various theoretical possibilities and inferences will be immature until further work is done in this field. Such a work is in progress. It may be pointed out here how this curve affords explanation of some observations with gels. In attempting to apply these results to other systems, we have to note that the solubility curve for other substances need not be of the shape observed for shellac and may not have the same degree of reversibility, whereas the gelation line will be more or less of this type for most substances except perhaps the inverse gel-forming ones (*e.g.* methylcellulose in water). Various possibilities may then occur for the ways in which the precipitation curve and the gelation curve would intersect each other giving rise to various types of peculiar phenomena. The more the solubility line tends to assume the usual shape, the more the region of unstable gelation would expand, and at times, this may come down to ordinary temperature. This is perhaps the reason why transparent gels of many substances, *e.g.*, dibenzoyl *l*-cystine, barium malonate, salts of organic acids, etc. have so strong tendency to separate amorphous or crystalline precipitate on keeping.

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